

Antidiabetic activity of some synthesized 2-(substituted phenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-ones

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Abstract : The title compounds (Tz₁₋₁₀) were synthesized by the reaction of thioglycolic acid on Schiff's bases (L₁₋₁₀) formed with 1-naphthylamine and substituted benzaldehydes. These were characterized on the basis of IR, NMR, Mass spectral and elemental analyses. The compounds were then evaluated for their antidiabetic activity using streptozotocin induced diabetes method. On screening, compounds Tz₁, Tz₄, Tz₅ and Tz₆ exhibited good antidiabetic activity.

Keywords : 4-Thiazolidinone, antidiabetics, streptozotocin, Schiff's base, naphthylamine.

Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is one of the major causes of mortality and morbidity worldwide. It is a chronic, heterogenous condition characterised by the disturbance in carbohydrate, lipid and protein metabolism that may be due to deficiency of insulin or resistance to the action of insulin at cellular level¹. At present, the treatment of diabetes mellitus includes drugs like biguanides, sulfonylureas, meglitinides, thiazolidinediones, α -glucosidase inhibitors in addition to insulin. Well established drugs like Rosiglitazone, Pioglitazone are a class of antidiabetic agents which have thiazolidinedione ring in them. These acts through peroxisome proliferator activated receptor γ (PPAR γ), which enhances the transcription of several responsive genes and tend to reverse insulin resistance by stimulating GLUT4 expression and translocation that improves the entry of glucose into muscle and fat². There is always a need for new antidiabetic agents due to untoward side effects of most of the effective agents.

Thiazolidinone, the nucleus of the present work possesses structural resemblance with thiazolidinedione antidiabetics, with only the absence of one ketonic group. Out of 2-, 3- and 4-oxo, thiazolidinones with

4-oxo are associated with numerous biological activities which include antidiabetic^{3,4}, anticonvulsant⁵⁻⁷, analgesic and anti-inflammatory⁸⁻¹⁰, antioxidant¹¹, hypnotic^{12,13}, antitubercular¹⁴, anti-HIV^{15,16}, antiparkinsonian¹⁷, anti-arthritis¹⁸, antimicrobial¹⁹⁻²¹, anti-amoebic²², antitumour^{23,24} activities. Due to these biological roles of 4-thiazolidinone analogs cited, it was planned to synthesize a few substituted thiazolidinones and to evaluate them for antidiabetic effects.

Out of the positions available for substitution in 4-thiazolidinone i.e. **2**, **3** and **5**, the positions 2 and 3 are important as evidenced by the numerous studies²⁴⁻²⁶. This led us to substitute carbon at position 2 and nitrogen at position 3 of thiazolidin-4-one ring. Thus it was worthwhile thought to synthesize title compounds which have naphthyl substituent at 3 and substituted phenyl at 2 positions in order to find new potent antidiabetic agents.

Results and discussion

In this study, ten novel thiazolidin-4-ones containing substituted phenyl ring at 2nd position and naphthalenyl moiety at 3rd position were synthesized and evaluated for antidiabetic activity.

Chemistry :

Schiff's bases (L_{1-10}) as prepared were reacted with thioglycolic acid in 1,4-dioxane in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride to give substituted thiazolidin-4-ones (Tz_{1-10}). Compounds were characterized by spec-

Tz_1 : R = 4-Cl; Tz_2 : R = 4-OH; Tz_3 : R = 4-CH₃; Tz_4 : R = 4-OCH₃; Tz_5 : R = 4-F; Tz_6 : R = 4-NO₂; Tz_7 : R = 4-N(CH₃)₂; Tz_8 : R = 2,5-OCH₃; Tz_9 : R = 3,4-OCH₃; Tz_{10} : R = 3-OCH₃, 4-OH.

Fig. 1. Scheme for synthesis of title compounds (Tz_1 - Tz_{10}).

tral (IR, ¹³C NMR and Mass) and elemental analyses. The IR, ¹³C NMR and Mass spectra of these substituted thiazolidinone (Tz_{1-10}) showed the expected frequencies and signals and the percentages of elements were found to be very near to that of the calculated values. The IR spectra of compounds Tz_{1-10} showed characteristic absorption for the carbonyl group at around 1680 cm⁻¹. In ¹³C NMR spectra (Tz_{1-10}), the signals appearing in the range of δ 168.3–173.4 ppm and δ 31.8–36.6 ppm, supported the presence of carbonyl group and methylene carbon thiazolidinone respectively. Mass spectral data of all the synthesized compounds were in agreement with their proposed molecular weights.

Antidiabetic activity :

All the compounds showed remarkable antidiabetic activity (Figs. 2, 3) at a dose level of 100 mg/kg. Compounds Tz_1 , Tz_4 , Tz_5 and Tz_6 exhibited excellent antidiabetic activity. On the other hand, compound Tz_7 , Tz_2 and Tz_3 exhibited poor to moderate antidiabetic activity.

A comparison of the biological activity with the structures showed that thiazolidinones (Tz_{1-10}) containing aromatic ring substituted with electron withdrawing group were better antidiabetic agents as compared to that are substituted with electron donating group. Compounds having *p*-chlorophenyl (Tz_1), *p*-methoxyphenyl (Tz_4), *p*-fluorophenyl (Tz_5) and *p*-nitrophenyl (Tz_6) attached to 2nd position of 3-naphthalenylthiazolidin-4-one emerged as potentially active antidiabetic agents. However those disubstituted with methoxy group (Tz_8 , Tz_9) were found to be moderately active as antidiabetic agent. Moreover, thiazolidinone containing aromatic ring substituted with *p*-dimethylamino group (Tz_7) was weakly active as antidiabetic agent.

Conclusion

Thus 4-thiazolidinone derivatives substituted at N-3 position with naphthyl and at C-2 position with aromatic ring having an electron withdrawing substituent were evolved as good antidiabetic agents. Further studies, with variations in the structure of thiazolidinone

Fig. 2. Antidiabetic effect of Glibenclamide and title compounds (Tz₁-Tz₁₀) on 1st, 3rd, 7th and 14th day. Values are expressed as mean ± S.D, a = $p < 0.05$ vs normal; b = $p < 0.05$ vs diabetic control; c = $p < 0.05$ vs standard drug (Glibenclamide treated).

Fig. 3. Antidiabetic effect of Glibenclamide and title compounds (Tz₁-Tz₁₀) on 1st and 14th day. Values are expressed as mean ± S.D, a = $p < 0.05$ vs normal; b = $p < 0.05$ vs diabetic control; c = $p < 0.05$ vs standard drug (Glibenclamide treated).

will increase the field and will lead to some definite conclusion which can be further worked upon for antidiabetic activity. However, more extensive studies are required to gain deeper insight into structure activity relationship and to optimize effectiveness of this

series of synthesized thiazolidinones. The research is also open to search and optimize the affinity of such compounds on receptor sites using *in silico* study. The extension of the study goes to discover new strategies for pharmacokinetic and toxicological studies.

Experimental

Chemicals, reagents and apparatus :

All the commercially available reagents were used without further purification. Melting points of compounds were determined in open capillaries and uncorrected. IR spectra (in KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR Affinity-1 FTIR spectrophotometer, using DRS 8000A accessory technique. ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded (CDCl_3) on a Jeol (500 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference standard (chemical shift values expressed in ppm on δ scale). The Mass spectra were recorded on a Bruker Daltonics micro TOF-Q II using EI method. Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were performed on Perkin-Elmer 2400 analyser. The completion of reaction and the purity of the synthesized compounds were routinely checked by Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) on silica gel G coated glass plates using iodine vapours as visualising agent and chloroform : ethanol (7 : 3) as eluant.

Experimental procedures :

The reaction pathway used and the substitutions on the title compounds has been summarized in Fig. 1.

General procedure for the synthesis of N-(substituted benzylidene)naphthalen-1-amine (Schiff's bases) (L_{1-10}) :

1-Naphthylamine (**1**) (0.02 mole, 2.86 g) and appropriate benzaldehydes (**2**) (0.02 mole) were taken in ethanol (25.0 mL) and refluxed for 2 h with 0.5 mL of glacial acetic acid. After cooling, the contents were poured onto crushed ice. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol²⁷.

General procedure for the synthesis of 2-(substituted phenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz_{1-10}) :

L_{1-10} (0.01 mole) was dissolved in 1,4-dioxane (25.0 mL) and then thioglycolic acid (0.01 mole, 0.7 mL) and a pinch of anhydrous zinc chloride were added. It was then refluxed for 8 h. The solution was poured onto crushed ice after cooling. The solids which separated out were filtered off and washed with water until freed from acid. The product was dried and recrystallized from ethanol^{27,28}.

2-(4-Chlorophenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz_1) :

Yield : 69.51%, m.p. 110–112°, R_f : 0.72. Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClNOS}$) : Calcd. : C, 67.15; H, 4.15; N, 4.12. Found : C, 67.12; H, 4.13; N, 4.15%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3051 (Ar C-H str.), 1673 (C=O str.), 1354 (C-N str.), 770 (C-Cl str.), 759 (C-S str.); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 171.2 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 141.9, 138.8, 131.1, 130.2, 129.8, 127.0, 126.5, 116.3, 112.5, 65.9 (C_2 , thiazolidinone), 35.3 (C_5 , thiazolidinone); MS m/z : 339.04 [M^+], 341.02 [$\text{M}+2$]⁺.

2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz_2) :

Yield : 98.59%, m.p. 130°, R_f : 0.50. Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$) : Calcd. C, 71.00; H, 4.70; N, 4.36. Found : C, 71.06; H, 4.67; N, 4.39%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3360 (Ar O-H str.), 3061 (Ar C-H str.), 1678 (C=O str.), 1372 (C-N str.), 754 (C-S str.); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 170.5 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 156.3, 131.1, 130.2, 127.0, 126.5, 125.0, 119.1, 115.4, 104.2, 58.6 (C_2 , thiazolidinone), 36.6 (C_5 , thiazolidinone); MS m/z : 321.08 [M^+], 322.06 [$\text{M}+1$]⁺.

3-(Naphthalen-1-yl)-2-p-tolylthiazolidin-4-one (Tz_3) :

Yield : 78.05%, m.p. 114–115°, R_f : 0.70. Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NOS}$) : Calcd. : C, 75.20; H, 5.36; N, 4.39. Found : C, 75.23; H, 5.31; N, 4.42%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3051 (Ar C-H str.), 2954 (asym. alip. C-H str.), 2914 (sym. alip. C-H str.), 1681 (C=O str.), 1372 (C-N str.), 754 (C-S str.); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 168.3 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 141.7, 138.8, 128.8, 127.0, 126.5, 106.3, 63.3 (C_2 , thiazolidinone), 34.5 (C_5 , thiazolidinone), 22.3; MS m/z : 319.10 [M^+], 320.02 [$\text{M}+1$]⁺.

2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz_4) :

Yield : 79.55%, m.p. 127–128°, R_f : 0.61. Elemental analysis ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2\text{S}$) : Calcd. : C, 79.57; H, 5.18; N, 4.64. Found : C, 79.61; H, 5.13; N, 4.68%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3063 (Ar C-H str.), 1675 (C=O str.), 1393 (C-N str.), 1033 (C-O-C str., ether), 752 (C-S str.); ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3) δ ppm : 173.4

(C=O, thiazolidinone), 160.2, 131.1, 130.2, 128.2, 114.6, 65.2 (C₂, thiazolidinone), 51.5, 33.2 (C₅, thiazolidinone); MS *m/z* : 335.09 [M⁺], 336.01 [M+1]⁺.

2-(4-Fluorophenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz₅) :

Yield : 79.56%, m.p. 114–115°, *R_f* : 0.63. Elemental analysis (C₁₉H₁₄FNOS) : Calcd. : C, 70.57; H, 4.36; N, 4.33. Found : C, 70.61; H, 4.31; N, 4.37%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3054 (Ar C-H str.), 1680 (C=O str.), 1372 (C-N str.), 1120 (Ar C-F str.), 753 (C-S str.); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 168.3 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 160.3, 136.4, 131.1, 130.2, 127.0, 126.5, 113.5, 106.3, 63.3 (C₂, thiazolidinone), 34.5 (C₅, thiazolidinone); MS *m/z* : 327.17 [M⁺], 328.12 [M+1]⁺.

2-(4-Nitrophenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz₆) :

Yield : 80.82%, m.p. 145–146°, *R_f* : 0.58. Elemental analysis (C₁₉H₁₄N₂O₃S) : Calcd. : C, 65.13; H, 4.03; N, 7.99. Found : C, 65.19; H, 4.06; N, 7.92%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3071 (Ar C-H str.), 1685 (C=O str.), 1517 (sym. NO₂ str.), 1392 (C-N str.), 1346 (asym. NO₂ str.), 755 (C-S str.); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 172.2 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 148.4, 146.3, 131.1, 129.4, 127.0, 126.5, 123.1, 101.4, 65.3 (C₂, thiazolidinone), 32.9 (C₅, thiazolidinone); MS *m/z* : 350.07 [M⁺], 351.10 [M+1]⁺.

2-(4-(Dimethylamino)phenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz₇) :

Yield : 90.08%, m.p. 125°, *R_f* : 0.66. Elemental analysis (C₂₁H₂₀N₂OS) : Calcd. : C, 72.38; H, 5.79; N, 8.04. Found : C, 72.32; H, 5.84; N, 8.01%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3060 (Ar C-H str.), 2960 (asym. alip. C-H str.), 2835 (sym. alip. C-H str.), 1688 (C=O str.), 1397 (C-N str.), 759 (C-S str.); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 170.4 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 138.8, 131.1, 128.6, 127.0, 126.5, 112.5, 102.8, 66.6 (C₂, thiazolidinone), 41.3, 33.6 (C₅, thiazolidinone); MS *m/z* : 348.13 [M⁺], 349.02 [M+1]⁺.

2-(2,5-Dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz₈) :

Yield : 66.57%, m.p. 115–116°, *R_f* : 0.53. Ele-

mental analysis (C₂₁H₁₉NO₃S) : Calcd. : C, 69.02; H, 5.24; N, 3.83. Found : C, 69.07; H, 5.21; N, 3.88%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3056 (Ar C-H str.), 1677 (C=O str.), 1377 (C-N str.), 1046 (C-O-C str., ether), 755 (C-S str.); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 173.3 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 131.1, 130.2, 127.0, 126.5, 116.3, 113.7, 112.5, 67.1 (C₂, thiazolidinone), 56.8, 55.2, 32.5 (C₅, thiazolidinone); MS *m/z* : 365.10 [M⁺], 366.04 [M+1]⁺.

2-(3,4-Dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz₉) :

Yield : 93.28%, m.p. 130–132°, *R_f* : 0.54. Elemental analysis (C₂₁H₁₉NO₃S) : Calcd. : C, 69.02; H, 5.24; N, 3.83. Found : C, 69.07; H, 5.21; N, 3.88%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3060 (Ar C-H str.), 1681 (C=O str.), 1397 (C-N str.), 1037 (C-O-C str., ether), 752 (C-S str.); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 170.5 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 149.3, 147.8, 131.1, 127.0, 126.5, 113.6, 112.5, 67.3 (C₂, thiazolidinone), 55.5, 31.8 (C₅, thiazolidinone); MS *m/z* : 365.10 [M⁺], 366.14 [M+1]⁺.

2-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-3-(naphthalen-1-yl)thiazolidin-4-one (Tz₁₀) :

Yield : 86.32%, m.p. 152–153°, *R_f* : 0.47. Elemental analysis (C₂₀H₁₇NO₃S) : Calcd. : C, 68.36; H, 4.88; N, 3.99. Found : C, 68.39; H, 4.84; N, 3.93%; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 3025 (Ar C-H str.), 1679 (C=O str.), 1393 (C-N str.), 1032 (C-O-C str., ether), 757 (C-S str.); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ ppm : 171.2 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 147.3, 131.1, 127.0, 126.5, 116.3, 112.5, 63.8 (C₂, thiazolidinone), 55.1, 34.8 (C₅, thiazolidinone); MS *m/z* : 351.09 [M⁺], 352.12 [M+1]⁺.

Antidiabetic activity :

Experimental animals :

Male Wistar rats (250–300 g) were used in this study. Animals were maintained under standard environmental conditions i.e. temperature of 25 ± 1°, relative humidity of 45–55% and 12 h light and 12 h dark cycle. They were fed with standard pellet diet and water was supplied *ad libitum*. All the studies were conducted under the conditions of the Animal Scientific Procedures. The experimental protocol was ap-

proved by the University Animal Ethical Committee of GLA University, Institute of Pharmaceutical Research, Mathura, UP, India (Approval no. GLAIPR/CPCSEA/IAEC/2013/P.Chem/5).

Induction of experimental diabetes :

Experimental diabetes was induced by streptozotocin²⁹. Food was withdrawn for 24 h before the experiment and water was allowed *ad libitum*. The rats were housed in spacious cages and divided into 13 groups, comprising of 6 rats in each group (one normal control, one diabetic control, one standard and ten test groups (Tz₁-Tz₁₀)). Diabetes was induced by single intraperitoneal injection of freshly prepared solution of streptozotocin (60 mg/kg b.w.) in 0.1 mol/L citrate buffer (pH 4.5). Normal control rats were injected with citrate buffer alone. The rats were allowed 5% w/v glucose solution orally for the next 24 h to prevent sudden hypoglycaemia³⁰. After 72 h, blood samples were collected by puncturing the retro orbital sinus using capillary glass tubes after anaesthetizing with ether and blood glucose level was determined by glucose test kit (Enzymatic, GOD-POD method) (Span Diagnostics Ltd., Surat, Gujarat, India) to determine the diabetic status. Rats having blood glucose greater than 200 mg/dL were considered as diabetic and used for further study.

Evaluation of blood glucose lowering effect of Tz₁₋₁₀ compounds :

The standard drug Glibenclamide (5 mg/kg b.w.) and test compounds (100 mg/kg b.w.) were suspended in 0.5% carboxymethylcellulose (CMC). The drug treatment was carried out orally using oral gavage for 14 days. Normal control and diabetic control rats were given only 0.5% CMC. During this period, all groups had free access to standard diet and water. Blood glucose level was determined on 1st, 3rd, 7th and 14th day of drug treatment after one hour of drug administration.

Statistical analysis :

The values are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. The results were analyzed for statistical significance using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Dunnet's test; $P < 0.01$ was considered significant.

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References

1. K. N. Anderson, L. E. Anderson and W. D. Glanze. "Mosby's Medical, Nursing, and Allied Health Dictionary", 4th ed., St. Louis, Mosby, 1994.
2. K. D. Tripathi, "Essential of Medical Pharmacology", 3rd ed., Jaypee Bothers, New Delhi, 2003.
3. S. D. Firke, B. M. Firake, R. Y. Chaudhari and V. R. Patil, *Asian J. Res. Chem.*, 2009, **2**, 157.
4. R. Ottana, R. Maccari, M. Giglio, A. D. Corso, M. Cappiello, U. Mura, S. Cosconati, L. Marinelli, E. Novellino, S. Sartini, C. L. Motta and F. D. Settimo, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **46**, 2797.
5. A. Gursoy and N. Terzioglu, *Turk. J. Chem.*, 2005, **29**, 247.
6. M. K. Gireesha, M. Irfanali, N. Srinivasulu and N. K. Sathish, *Orient J. Chem.*, 2010, **26**, 941.
7. V. Velmurugan, N. Leelavathi, S. Kalvikkarasi, S. S. Priya and M. V. Aanandhi, *Int. J. Chem. Tech. Res.*, 2012, **4**, 1.
8. J. Hu, Y. Wang, X. Wei, X. Wu, G. Chen, G. Cao, X. Shen, X. Zhang, Q. Tang, G. Liang and X. Li, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2013, **64**, 292.
9. S. Sharma, T. Singh, R. Mittal, K. K. Saxena and V. K. Srivastava, *Arch. Pharm. Chem. Life Sci.*, 2006, **339**, 145.
10. A. Deep, S. Jain, P. C. Sharma, S. K. Mittal, P. Phogat and M. Malhotra, *Med. Chem. Res.*, 2012, **21**, 1652.
11. A. Adhikari, B. Kalluraya, K. V. Sujith, K. Gouthamchandra and R. Mahmood, *J. Adv. Res.*, 2012, **3**, 325.
12. S. K. Chaudhari, M. Verma, A. K. Chaturvedi and S. S. Parmar, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1975, **64**, 614.
13. M. Chaudhary, S. S. Parmar, S. K. Chaudhary, A. K. Chaturvedi and B. V. Rama Sastry, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1976, **65**, 443.
14. V. P. Trivedi, N. K. Undavia and P. B. Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **81**, 506.
15. J. Balzarini, B. Orzeszko, J. K. Maurin and A. Orzeszko, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **42**, 993.
16. V. Ravichandran, B. R. P. Kumar, S. Sankar and R. K. Agrawal, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **44**, 1180.
17. S. Kumar, H. Kaur, K. K. Saxena, M. Sharma, P. Vishwakarma and A. Kumar, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2010, **49B**, 1398.

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18. A. M. Panico, P. Vicini, A. Geronikaki, M. Incerti, V. Cardile, L. Crasci, R. Messina and S. Ronsisvalle, *Bioorg. Chem.*, 2011, **39**, 48.
19. A. P. Liesen, T. M. Aquino, V. T. Lima, C. S. Carvaloh, V. T. Lima, J. M. de Arujo, J. G. de Lima, A. R. de Faria, E. J. de Melo, A. J. Alves, E. W. Alves, A. Q. Alves and A. J. Goes, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **45**, 3685.
20. H. Chen, Y. Li, J. Bai, L. Zhao, X. Yuan, X. Li and K. Cao, *Front Chem. Eng. China*, 2009, **3**, 186.
21. P. Vicini, A. Geronikaki, M. Incerti, F. Zani, J. Dearden and M. Hewitt, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2008, **16**, 3714.
22. M. Mushtaque, F. Avecilla and A. Ajam, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2012, **55**, 439.
23. S. Wang, Y. Zhao, G. Zhang, N. Zhang and P. Gong, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **46**, 3509.
24. D. Havrylyuk, L. Mosula, B. Zimenkovsky, O. Vasylenko, A. Gzella and R. Lesyk, *Eur. J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **46**, 5012.
25. D. Havrylyuk, B. Zimenkovsky, O. Vasylenko, A. Gzella and R. Lesyk, *Med. Chem.*, 2012, **55**, 8630.
26. D. Havrylyuk, B. Zimenkovsky, O. Vasylenko and R. Lesyk, *J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2013, **50**, E55.
27. S. V. More, D. V. Dongarkhadekar, W. N. Chavan, W. N. Jadhav, S. R. Bhusare and R. P. Pawar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2002, **79**, 768.
28. C. K. Ramaganesh, D. B. Yadav and K. B. Venkatesh, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2010, **49B**, 1151.
29. A. Akbarzadeh, D. Norouzian, M. R. Mehrabi, S. Jamshidi, A. Farhangi, A. A. Verdi, S. M. A. Mofidian and B. L. Rad, *Indian J. Clin. Biochem.*, 2007, **22**, 60.
30. R. S. Somani and A. K. Singhai, *Asian J. Exp. Sci.*, 2008, **22**, 95.

